

NaT-ReX: Naturalness Assessment with Transformer-Based Reliable Explainability*

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Abstract. Protected natural areas, minimally affected by modern human influence, are essential for ecological stability and processes such as water cycles and pollination. A continuous and efficient monitoring of these areas has become increasingly important, and machine learning and satellite imagery offer new opportunities for getting insights and assessing their naturalness. However, current approaches rely on predefined assumptions of naturalness or do not account for model uncertainty, limiting robustness and interpretability of the results. We propose NaT-ReX, a Transformer-based Reliable Explainability framework that integrates explainable machine learning with uncertainty quantification. NaT-ReX highlights areas that are reliably associated with naturalness while discounting regions with higher uncertainty. To support this, we introduce the ReX score, a novel metric to evaluate both pixel-wise relevance to naturalness and land cover classes based on their contributions to naturalness and the associated uncertainty. Our experiments on two satellite datasets—AnthroProtect and MapInWild—demonstrate both qualitative and quantitative insights. Our findings demonstrate that shrublands and wetlands contribute the most to naturalness, while open water and snow-dominated regions exhibit the lowest ReX scores due to higher uncertainty or lower semantic attribution. These findings align with both data-driven and expert-informed assessments of naturalness, highlighting the potential of NaT-ReX as an efficient and uncertainty-aware monitoring and analysis framework.

Keywords: Explainable Machine Learning (XAI) · Uncertainty Quantification · Naturalness · Wilderness

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1 Introduction

Areas of minimal human influence play a critical role in preserving ecological stability, supporting biodiversity, and maintaining essential ecosystem services such as water cycles, pollination, and habitat provision[27],[5]. In addition to their environmental importance, these regions offer cultural, recreational, and educational value, reinforcing the need for their protection and sustainable management [3].

Fig. 1. Inference pipeline of the NaT-ReX framework. The input image is passed through the shared encoder \mathcal{F} , producing two outputs: an uncertainty map from the reconstruction head \mathcal{G} using Monte Carlo Dropout, and an LRP attention map from the classification head \mathcal{S} via attention rollout. These two outputs are integrated per pixel using the ReX formulation to generate the final ReX map, which highlights spatial contributions to the class **naturalness** while accounting for uncertainty.

It is essential to monitor and analyze these natural areas at scale. Satellite remote sensing provides a powerful means for doing so, offering high-resolution, multispectral observations across large and often inaccessible regions. Such imagery enables researchers to track land cover changes, vegetation dynamics, and other ecological indicators over time. However, characterizing naturalness from satellite data remains challenging. Human impact on ecosystems often occurs gradually, and the boundary between natural and anthropogenically influenced areas is not always clear. Traditional mapping approaches with rigid classifications may oversimplify the nuanced continuum between untouched and influenced states [30],[14].

Machine learning (ML) offers a promising solution for modeling such complexity. Techniques like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) extract spatial features from multispectral or temporal satellite data [26]. These models can be adapted for monitoring tasks such as land cover classification, environmental change detection, or pattern recognition [21]. Many machine learning-based approaches for assessing naturalness are black-box models, meaning they do not reveal how predictions are made. This lack of transparency is problematic in environmental applications, where understanding the reasoning behind a prediction is essential. Explainability methods allow us to see which parts of the input the model relies on, helping to verify whether the model focuses on meaningful ecological features. Without such tools, there is a risk that models make decisions based on irrelevant or misleading patterns — a problem demonstrated in the so-called Clever Hans effect, where models learn shortcuts that do not generalize well [20]. In addition, these approaches do not address the uncertainty associated with models or data. As a result, they may produce insights while they are unsure, leading to decisions based on outputs that may be overconfident or unreliable [17]. This combination — lack of explainability and missing uncertainty estimates limits the trustworthiness and robustness of naturalness assessments, especially when applied to sensitive or policy-relevant tasks.

To address these gaps, we propose NaT-ReX (see Fig. 1) with the following key contributions: (1) a framework that integrates explainability, in the form of propagated relevance, and uncertainty for naturalness investigation, (2) the ReX score that quantifies naturalness as uncertainty-weighted relevance, and (3) a qualitative and quantitative analysis of naturalness at both the pixel and class levels.

2 Related work

2.1 Naturalness Assessment

Efforts to assess naturalness have primarily focused on quantifying human influence to identify and protect minimally disturbed areas. Early work by Sanderson et al. (2002) [27] introduced the Human Influence Index (HII), which aggregates factors such as population density, land use, and road networks. The HII, based on data from the 1960s to 1990s at a 1 km² resolution, is widely used but limited by its coarse scale, lack of temporal adaptability, and reliance on static assumptions. Similarly, Winter et al. (2010) [32] proposed the Wilderness Quality Index for Europe, which incorporates terrain features but focuses mainly on forested ecosystems and does not produce spatially detailed outputs.

Ekim et al. [8], [9] extended this line of work by introducing the Naturalness Index (NI), which improved spatial resolution and integrated multimodal inputs such as Sentinel-1/2 bands, nightlight intensity, and land cover maps. While technically robust, the NI is partially guided by predefined assumptions—for instance, it assigns lower naturalness to shrublands and sparsely vegetated areas based on predefined beliefs. Such assumptions, while reasonable in certain contexts, may limit the index’s applicability in ecosystems where shrublands

are strong indicators of naturalness and highlight the need for more data-driven approaches.

Recent developments in machine learning (ML) and Earth observation (EO) offer more flexible and data-driven alternatives. CNN-based frameworks [30],[29], and generative approaches [14] have been used to analyze protected regions, revealing spatial patterns through activation-based methods. Building on this, Emam et al. (2024) [12] proposed the Confident Naturalness Explanation (CNE) framework, the first to combine explainability with uncertainty quantification for this task. The CNE score measures the confident contribution of specific patterns to naturalness.

Despite its novelty, CNE has key limitations: it flattens spatial input into 1D vectors for logistic regression, leading to a loss of spatial structure, and assigns scores only at the class level, not per patch. These research gaps emphasize the need for pixel-wise naturalness contributions, uncertainty-aware frameworks that avoid fixed assumptions and enable fine-grained naturalness assessments.

Table 1 summarizes the main contributions and limitations of these approaches.

2.2 Explainability and Uncertainty

Explainable machine learning (XAI) methods are commonly categorized into model-agnostic and model-specific approaches [2,18]. Model-agnostic techniques such as LIME [25] and SHAP [22] are adaptable to a wide range of models and offer local explanations of individual predictions. However, these methods can suffer from instability, high computational cost, and lack of spatial resolution when applied to high-dimensional inputs such as satellite imagery. Consequently, they are less suitable for spatially detailed and class-specific attribution in Earth observation tasks.

Model-specific explainability techniques, in contrast, exploit the structure of specific model architectures to provide more targeted and reliable explanations. A widely used method in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) is Grad-CAM [28], which generates class-specific saliency maps based on gradients flowing through convolutional layers. While effective for image-level classification, Grad-CAM often produces low-resolution heatmaps. Emam et al. [11] proposed a framework to compare models based on how well their explanations align with domain knowledge, evaluating different architectures and explainability methods.

In transformer-based models, particularly Vision Transformers (ViTs) [7], explainability presents unique challenges due to the absence of convolutional layers and the use of self-attention mechanisms. To address this, Chefer et al. [6] introduced a transformer-specific adaptation of Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) that propagates class-specific relevance scores through the attention layers. This method, known as LRP attention rollout, provides high-resolution attribution maps that maintain the spatial context of input patches and identify the most relevant regions contributing to a specific class. In our framework,

Table 1. Summary of Related Work in Naturalness Assessment

Publication	Key Features	Limitations
Sanderson et al. (2002) [27]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantifies global human impact. - Uses factors such as population density, land use, and road access. - Broad-scale assessment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low spatial and temporal resolution. - Relies on predefined assumptions. - Lacks detailed representation of ecological patterns.
Winter et al. (2010) [32]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasizes wilderness quality across Europe. - Uses terrain ruggedness and remoteness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited generalizability beyond study region. - No temporal or pixel-level resolution.
Ekim et al. (2021) [8]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides higher spatial resolution (10 m). - Incorporates refined land cover and accessibility data. - Suitable for regional assessments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relies on subjective assumptions of naturalness. - Potential misalignment with local domain knowledge. - Sensitive to cultural/regional interpretations.
Ekim (2024) [9]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporates multimodal inputs (Sentinel-1/2, nightlights, land cover). - Enhances the depth of naturalness assessment. - Builds upon the Naturalness Index (NI). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Still relies on predefined assumptions. - May introduce bias due to cultural or regional subjectivity.
Stomberg et al. (2022, 2023) [30,29]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses CNNs for pixel-level analysis of satellite data. - Highlights protected and impacted patterns in imagery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Occludes activations in a specific layer, leading to inconsistency when the layer changes. - Sensitive to size and placement of sliding occlusion window. - Focuses on identifying patterns but not full explanations.
Emam et al. (2024) [14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses adversarial generative training and activation maximization. - Produces high-resolution and interpretable heatmaps. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High computational cost due to dual GAN networks and a regressor. - Lacks uncertainty quantification in data or architecture.
Emam et al. (2024) [12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduces the Confident Naturalness Explanation (CNE) score. - Combines relevance and uncertainty into a single metric. - Provides pixel-level uncertainty visualization. - Integrates domain knowledge for interpretability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Converts images to 1D vectors, losing spatial context. - Scores limited to land cover classes, not individual patches. - High computational cost due to Monte Carlo sampling.
NaT-ReX Framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserves spatial structure using a transformer-based encoder. - Uses LRP attention rollout to identify pixel-level contributions to naturalness. - Integrates pixel-level uncertainty via MC-Dropout. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires multiple forward passes for Monte Carlo sampling, increasing inference time. - Captures only epistemic uncertainty. - May require better uncertainty methods for critical applications.

we adopt LRP attention rollout to generate pixel-level relevance for the class **naturalness**, allowing spatially fine-grained interpretation of model decisions.

Complementary to explainability, uncertainty quantification (UQ) provides a measure of the model’s confidence in its predictions, which is critical in sensitive domains like environmental monitoring and land use assessment. Among the many UQ techniques, Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs)[17] offer a theoretically grounded framework for estimating uncertainty but are computationally intractable in large models. Scalable approximations such as Monte Carlo Dropout (MC-Dropout) [16] and deep ensembles [19] have been widely adopted to estimate epistemic uncertainty—the uncertainty due to limited data or model capacity.

In this work, we estimate uncertainty by applying MC-Dropout in the reconstruction head of the NaT-ReX framework. By performing multiple stochastic forward passes of the same input image, we compute the pixel-wise variance across reconstructions, which serves as a proxy for epistemic uncertainty. This allows us to quantify how confidently the model reconstructs each region of the input, providing an interpretable uncertainty map at high spatial resolution.

Recent work has begun to explore the integration of explainability and uncertainty to improve model reliability. For instance, Mehdiyev et al. [23] combined total predictive uncertainty with feature attribution for complex systems, and B-LRP [4] extended relevance propagation to Bayesian models to estimate explanation confidence. However, these approaches are either limited to CNNs or require computationally expensive Bayesian frameworks. In contrast, our NaT-ReX framework employs a transformer-based encoder with dual heads: one using LRP attention rollout for explainability, the other leveraging MC-Dropout-based reconstruction for pixel-wise uncertainty. This setup enables fine-grain, uncertainty-aware relevance scoring for naturalness assessment, offering uncertainty-aware, interpretable analysis of naturalness. Emam et al. [13] recently proposed the Confidence-Filtered Relevance (CFR) framework to analyze how model uncertainty influences the interpretability of relevance heatmaps. Their results show that with increasing uncertainty, the entropy of the relevance distribution grows, indicating less selective and more ambiguous attributions. This demonstrates that higher epistemic uncertainty reduces the clarity of explanations, reinforcing the need for uncertainty-aware interpretability in naturalness assessment.

3 Methodology

3.1 NaT-ReX Architecture and Training Strategy

NaT-ReX is built on a Vision Transformer (ViT-B/16) encoder [7] and includes two output heads trained jointly in a multitask setup: a classification head for predicting the class **naturalness** versus **non-naturalness** and a reconstruction head for image reconstruction. The use of a transformer encoder allows the model to capture long-range dependencies and global context, which are critical for scene-level understanding in naturalness assessment. See Figure 2

The classification head is a fully connected layer that outputs a score for each class. During inference, we apply Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) to the naturalness score to identify the regions of the image that contributed most to the prediction. The reconstruction head transforms the encoder’s output back into the original image layout. Tokens are reshaped into image patches and passed through three convolutional layers—two with ReLU activations—to improve reconstruction quality.

Training is performed end-to-end using a combined loss: a cross-entropy loss for the classification head and a mean squared error loss for the reconstruction head. This multitask formulation encourages the encoder to learn spatial features that support both attribution and uncertainty quantification in the inference stage.

Fig. 2. Training architecture of the NaT-ReX framework. The input satellite image is processed by a Vision Transformer-based encoder \mathcal{F} , which feeds into two parallel heads: a reconstruction head \mathcal{G} that learns to reconstruct the input image, and a classification head \mathcal{S} that predicts **naturalness** versus **non-naturalness**. Both heads are trained simultaneously in a multi-task learning setup to optimize both classification and reconstruction objectives.

Classification Head: Relevance to Naturalness via LRP Attention Roll-out To generate class-specific relevance maps, we use the attention-based Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) method adapted for Vision Transformers by Chefer et al. [6]. This method propagates relevance scores from the classification output back through the attention layers. Unlike standard attention rollout[1], which produces unguided and less interpretable heatmaps, our approach highlights features that specifically contribute to the **naturalness** class. Figure 3 (bottom) highlights the image regions contributing to both the **naturalness** and **non-naturalness** classes.

Let $A^{(b)}$ denote the attention matrix in transformer block b , and $R^{(n_b)}$ the relevance at that layer’s output. The adjusted attention map is defined as:

$$\bar{A}^{(b)} = I + \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \max\left(\nabla A_h^{(b)} \odot R_h^{(n_b)}, 0\right) \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 updates the attention in block b by averaging the gradient-based relevance across all attention heads, keeping only positive contributions. The identity matrix I ensures residual connections are preserved, allowing each token to retain part of its own relevance.

The final relevance map is computed as:

$$M = \bar{A}^{(1)} \cdot \bar{A}^{(2)} \cdot \dots \cdot \bar{A}^{(B)} \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 accumulates relevance across all transformer blocks, effectively tracing how importance propagates from the model’s output back to the input tokens. For a detailed derivation, we refer the reader to Chefer et al. [6].

Reconstruction Head: Uncertainty Quantification via MC-Dropout To estimate epistemic uncertainty, we use Monte Carlo Dropout (MC-Dropout) in the reconstruction head. During inference, J stochastic forward passes are performed with dropout enabled, producing a set of slightly varied reconstructions.

Let $Y_{h,w,c,j}$ be the reconstructed pixel value at position (h, w, c) from the j^{th} forward pass. The pixel-wise mean is:

$$\bar{Y}_{h,w,c} = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J Y_{h,w,c,j} \quad (3)$$

And the corresponding uncertainty estimate is the standard deviation:

$$S_{h,w,c} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J (Y_{h,w,c,j} - \bar{Y}_{h,w,c})^2} \quad (4)$$

The resulting uncertainty map $S \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ reflects the model’s epistemic uncertainty in reconstructing each pixel, with higher values indicating lower confidence.

ReX Score: Combining naturalness, relevancy, and Uncertainty The ReX score R_n measures how confidently a pixel n contributes to the class “naturalness,” combining its relevance and associated uncertainty:

$$R_n = \left[M_{\text{norm},n} \log \left(1 + \alpha \cdot \frac{1}{S_{\text{norm},n} + c} \right) \right]^\beta \quad (5)$$

Here, $M_{\text{norm},n}$ denotes the normalized LRP relevance for patch n , and $S_{\text{norm},n}$ represents the normalized pixel-wise uncertainty. The relevance map M_{norm} is

normalized using min-max scaling based on the minimum and maximum relevance values across the image. The logarithmic term penalizes high uncertainty, ensuring that only patches with both high relevance and low uncertainty receive high ReX scores. The parameters are set as follows: $\alpha = 0.5$ (controls the impact of uncertainty), $c = 0.2$ (sets a floor to prevent division by near-zero), and $\beta = 0.8$ (adjusts the sharpness of the score distribution).

This formulation results in pixel-wise uncertainty-aware contribution to naturalness, improving the robustness and interpretability of naturalness assessments. Figure 1 illustrates the inference pipeline and score calculation.

4 Data, Experiments, and Results

4.1 Datasets

AnthroProtect [30] and MapInWild [10] contain Sentinel-2 images from both preserved and unpreserved areas. Each image is associated with a binary label indicating whether it represents an area of *naturalness* or *non-naturalness* area. In addition, each image is accompanied by a land cover segmentation map, derived from CORINE [15] for AnthroProtect and ESA WorldCover [33] for MapInWild. AnthroProtect includes 23,919 images of size 256×256 from Fennoscandia, covering protected regions as a proxy for naturalness. We used 80% of the data for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing. For consistency, we selected scenes from the Fennoscandia region in the MapInWild dataset as well, since it offers relatively homogeneous ecological conditions and a clearly defined concept of naturalness. Importantly, the MapInWild dataset was not used in any part of the training process and serves purely as an unseen test set to evaluate generalization. Following Sanderson et al. [27], naturalness is biome-dependent: in Fennoscandia, vegetated areas are primary indicators of naturalness, whereas in regions like North Africa or the Arabian Peninsula, deserts are dominant contributors.

4.2 Experimental Setup

The NaT-ReX framework was trained on the AnthroProtect dataset using a multitask learning strategy. The classification head, responsible for predicting naturalness versus non-naturalness, was trained for 10 epochs and achieved 100% accuracy on the training dataset and 98% on the test dataset. The reconstruction head, which is used for pixel-wise uncertainty estimation, was trained for 30 epochs with an effective batch size of 16 and reached a best reconstruction loss of 0.129 and 0.133 for the training and test datasets, respectively. Training was performed using a batch size of 64.

In the first experiment, we computed the ReX score for each image patch in the AnthroProtect dataset to analyze pixel-level contributions to naturalness and the associated uncertainty. These scores were correlated with the provided land cover segmentation masks to determine the average ReX score of each land

cover class. For comparability, ReX values were normalized to the range $[0, 1]$, assigning 1.0 to the class with the highest confident contribution to naturalness and 0.0 to the lowest. In a second experiment, we evaluated the generalizability of the trained NaT-ReX model on the unseen MapInWild dataset. We calculated ReX scores for each pixel and correlated them with the corresponding land cover classes to determine the average ReX score per class. This allowed us to assess the model’s transferability and consistency across geographically and semantically distinct protected areas.

4.3 Results

Fig. 3. Top: NaT-ReX visualizations showing the original input, LRP attention maps for *naturalness*, MC-Dropout uncertainty maps, and resulting ReX maps. Bottom: CutMix visualizations used to evaluate class-specific relevance under mixed patch compositions. Column 1 and 3 shows CutMix images blending natural and urban regions. Columns 2 and 4 show LRP attention maps for *non-naturalness* in negative values and *naturalness* in positive values, respectively.

Qualitative Results Figure 3 presents two subplots. The bottom subplot illustrates different relevance signals derived from the same input image when processed by the ReX approach. Features such as croplands and urban areas exhibit high relevance toward the **non-naturalness** class, while vegetated regions and wetlands show high relevance for the **naturalness** class. The top subplot displays the weighted relevance for the **naturalness** class, where relevance is weighted by uncertainty. Regions with both high relevance and high certainty retain strong ReX scores, whereas areas with low relevance and high uncertainty are suppressed, resulting in lower ReX scores.

Fig. 4. Comparison of normalized naturalness-related indices across land cover classes. The indices include ReX (ours), which integrates relevance to naturalness and uncertainty; the Naturalness Index (NI) from Ekim et al. [8]; the Human influence index (HII) from Sanderson et al. [27], reversed to represent naturalness; and the Confident Naturalness Index (CNE) from Emam et al. [12], based on attribution scores filtered by model confidence. The plot highlights consistent patterns across indices, with shrubland, wetland, and forest classes ranked highest in naturalness, and water- and ice-related classes ranked lowest.

Quantitative Results All ReX scores were normalized to $[0, 1]$ for comparability across indices. Figure 4 presents a cross-index comparison of normalized naturalness scores across seven main land cover classes using four different indices: our ReX score, the Naturalness Index (NI) from Ekim et al. [8], the Human Influence Index (HII) from Sanderson et al. [27], and the Confident Naturalness

Explanation (CNE) score from Emam et al. [12]. The illustration shows clear trends: *shrubland*, *trees*, and *wetland* classes receive consistently high naturalness scores across indices, while *snow and ice* and *open water* score the lowest. ReX exhibits strong Pearson correlations with the other numerical indices: $r = 0.96$ with NI, $r = 0.924$ with HII, and $r = 0.970$ with CNE, indicating high consistency while also preserving key distinctions.

Despite the general alignment, certain differences emerge. For example, CNE assigns higher naturalness to *bare/sparse vegetation* than other indices. This discrepancy stems from the fact that CNE transforms satellite images into 1D vectors before applying logistic regression, thus discarding spatial context and structure. Similarly, both NI and HII rely on predefined expert assumptions of what constitutes **naturalness**, whereas our ReX framework derives its scores in a fully data-driven manner, grounded in learned semantic relevance to the concept of naturalness and the model confidence.

4.4 Limitations of NaT-ReX

NaT-ReX currently relies on Monte Carlo Dropout to approximate epistemic uncertainty, which requires multiple forward passes and increased inference cost. MC-Dropout captures only epistemic uncertainty and not aleatoric uncertainty arising from noise or inherent data ambiguity. This limitation is especially relevant in real-world conservation applications, where more complete uncertainty modeling is needed. Future work could explore deep ensembles[31], deterministic uncertainty models[24] to improve robustness under distribution shift.

5 Conclusion

We presented NaT-ReX, a transformer-based framework for assessing naturalness in satellite imagery by integrating explainability and uncertainty estimation. At its core is the ReX score, which combines LRP-based attention maps with pixel-level uncertainty from Monte Carlo Dropout. This allows relevance to be modulated by model confidence, enabling more robust and interpretable spatial analysis. NaT-ReX preserves spatial structure, avoids reliance on subjective assumptions, and assigns patch-level relevance scores. It is trained end-to-end and generalizes well across datasets, as consistent results on AnthroProtect and MapInWild show. Land cover types such as *transitional woodland-shrub*, *shrubland*, and *peat bogs* receive high ReX scores, while *snow and ice*, *open water*, and *bare rock* are down-weighted due to higher uncertainty or lower relevance to naturalness. These results align with prior explainability and expert-based studies. By combining spatial relevance to naturalness with uncertainty, NaT-ReX enables more transparent and reliable assessments of natural areas, supporting naturalness monitoring efforts.

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